

Kendo Headgear Concussion Safety Evaluation

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Abstract: Concussions present a potential risk in various contact sports, including the martial art of kendo. While there are regulations implemented on the production quality of shinai, the bamboo-based swords used in kendo, there is a lack of active standards enforced by an independent governing body for kendo armor to prevent head injuries like concussions. Interestingly, two separate independent governing bodies exist to regulate and ensure the quality of commercially-sold shinai, but none for armor. This study aimed to answer two important questions: firstly, whether high-end kendo helmets offer superior protection against concussions compared to entry-level helmets, and secondly, whether adding extra padding inserts to the helmets enhances overall concussion protection. To conduct the study, we asked several kendo practitioners and one non-practitioner to deliver a series of head strikes using a shinai on a mannequin wearing different kendo helmets, both with and without additional protective padding. Our objective was to measure the force of each strike and assess the associated risk of concussion. The results indicated that both types of helmets sustained linear accelerations well below the threshold for the risk of concussion, which is set at 62.4g force. Notably, there were no statistical differences regarding impact forces received between the helmets (p-value equals 0.13). Interestingly, we found that commercial helmet padding inserts did not significantly reduce the risk of concussion. In fact, one of the commercially made helmet inserts performed worse than using a helmet alone (p-value is less than 0.01). In summary, our study suggests that investing in an entry-level kendo helmet with a 4-mm stitch pattern can offer comparable concussion protection to a high-end helmet with a 2-mm stitch pattern. As for commercially available padding inserts, their potential to provide additional concussion protection remains inconclusive and further studies are needed. Implementing a standardized evaluation process can aid consumers in making informed decisions when selecting protective gear to prevent concussions.

Keywords: Kendo; Concussion; Sports Safety; Kendo Gears

I. INTRODUCTION

Sports-related concussions have recently gained much attention, particularly with regard to prevention and management. Efforts to prevent such concussions, seen primarily in

contact sports like rugby and soccer, have been implemented, including revising and creating guidelines for injury recovery^{1,2}. A study analyzing data from the National Collegiate Athletic Association (NCAA) in the US reported a higher incidence of sports-related concussions in contact sports such as wrestling,

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ice hockey, and American football³. Other studies investigating brain damage resulting from these types of concussions have also been conducted, such as measuring head impact using accelerometers⁴ or estimating brain injury risk through video analysis⁵. Mechanisms of concussion have also been explored using a baseline evaluation or blood biomarkers^{6,7}. However, most published studies on sports-related concussions have historically focused more on NCAA-sanctioned sports, such as American football and rugby. Few studies have been described in Western literature for the prevention of concussion in lesser-known Japanese contact sports, such as kendo (the Japanese art of fencing) and judo (the Japanese art of unarmed combat)⁸. Even in Japan, concussions are not well reported or studied in kendo⁹. Although these sports continue to cause numerous head injuries annually, research efforts have not been as extensively conducted in these sports¹⁰. Kendo, a relatively lesser-known full-contact sport in the Western world, is a form of Japanese martial art that utilizes a shinai (bamboo sword) and bogu (protective armor). The bogu consists of the men (helmet), do (body protector), kote (gloves), and tare (hip and groin protector). Scoring points in kendo are attained by striking specific protected areas of the body that include the head, neck, wrist, and torso¹⁰. Novice beginners in kendo often exhibit a tendency to strike with full force because it may feel more intuitive which is inappropriate in the sport/art. *Tenouchi* is a kendo technique that involves the art of gripping the handle of the sword to control and minimize the force applied. Only after beginners have learned *tenouchi*, are they permitted to wear bogu and engage in full contact practice with their opponents¹¹. Of note, previous studies conducted in Japan have utilized only kendo masters to collect data.

These more experienced kendo practitioners (4th dan / black belt equivalent and above) tend to have well-controlled *tenouchi* and presumably strike lighter with less force compared to a beginner¹⁰.

Skilled kendo practitioners typically execute lighter strikes on their opponents' heads, instead of swinging forcefully to minimize the risk of injury and excessive damage to the armor. In that regard, it is important to consider this distinction, as the skill level of the kendo practitioner can significantly influence the impact force of their strikes. However, concussions can still occur and are well documented in literature¹². See Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Kendo Protective Gear (A) do - body protector (B) men - helmet (C) tare - hip and groin protector (D) kote - gloves (E) shinai - bamboo sword.

With the increasing popularity of kendo, there has been a greater emphasis on the functionality of shinai and bogu, leading to modifications that have made competitions hazardous and unsafe. This trend involves reducing the weight of equipment to increase agility; for example, helmets are made thinner by using less protective padding material inside and shaving out the inside of the shinai¹². To counteract this trend, the All-Japan Kendo Federation made a committee statement in 2019 that introduced amendments to the Match

Referee Rules for Kendo Equipment to improve safety^{13,14}. This guideline established rules to regulate the thickness of the shinai tips and the length of the kendo robe sleeves, uniform, and equipment, ensuring a cushion to decrease the impact during matches. However, these regulations expect manufactures to self-police the quality of its products. There are no independent third-party organizations to verify the safety of these armors¹⁵ (only shinai manufacturing is certified and regulated by independent organizations¹⁶). In the absence of set regulations, consumers may gravitate towards pricier protective gear, assuming that it would offer better protection.

The lack of standardization in kendo equipment manufacturing has led to a wide range of products in the market. Our research seeks to address the questions: 1) Does a high-end (more expensive) kendo helmet offer more protection against concussions compared to an entry-level helmet, and 2) Does adding a padded insert improve the overall protection against concussions?

II. METHODOLOGY

An experiment was conducted on kendo protective headgear to assess the efficacy of both commercial brands for helmet pads and homemade versions in preventing concussions. This was done by reproducing the strike impact of a shinai on a mannequin head wearing one of many combinations of helmet or helmet plus padding. The resulting force from each strike inflicted on each protective headgear being tested was measured using a sensor (NET Playz Combat Force Tracker) installed within the mannequin head.

For this study, a mannequin head was attached to a 175 cm wooden post. Four kendo practitioners applied a series of strikes to the

mannequin, which was equipped with various helmets and head pads. The force of each strike was recorded using a combat force sensor positioned in the mannequin's head. See Figure 2. Of the four kendo practitioners, one was a non-kendo practitioner, two were beginners (7 kyu, 6 kyu) and one was a master (shodan/black belt equivalent).

The dimensions of the mannequin head were designed to match an average male head, with a height of 33 cm and a circumference of 57 cm^{17,18}. To replicate the natural position of the brain, we suspended the sensor used to measure the impact force in the middle of the mannequin head. The remaining space within the mannequin head was then filled with silicone. The final setup involved attaching the mannequin head wearing a helmet and head pad onto a wooden mount adjusted to a height of 175 cm, corresponding to the height of the kendo practitioner at 175 cm.

Two sets of protective helmets were used: a low-cost entry-level helmet (Entry-level) and a high-end helmet (High-end) for experienced kendo practitioners. The entry-level helmet featured 4-mm stitching and a steel grill, while the high-end helmet had 2-mm stitching and a titanium grill. Smaller stitching and titanium base grill typically indicate higher equipment costs.

Fig. 2. Study Setup - Kendo practitioner striking the mannequin equipped with protector gear and sensor. (Figure by Megan Hsu)

Fig. 3. Four types of protective paddings are placed inside the helmet. (C1) Commercial Pad 1, cotton-based. (C2) Commercial Pad 2, cotton-based. (H1) Homemade Pad 1, rubber-based. (H2) Homemade Pad 2-rubber, based airgel.

In addition to the helmets, various protective helmet paddings were assessed. These included two commercial and two homemade helmet pad inserts. The commercial helmet pads were made of cotton and differed only in size, with one marketed as “wide” (C1) and the other as “narrow” (C2). One of the homemade helmet pads was constructed by attaching two layers of anti-slip rubber tape between a standard plastic folder cut into the shape of a standard helmet pad insert (H1). The other homemade helmet pad insert was constructed from SHOCKtec® Air2Gel rubber material (H2). See Figure 3.

The collected data was initially measured in units of kg force and then converted to units of g force using the formula: $\text{kg force} / \text{mass (kg)} = \text{g force}$. To compare the levels of protection offered by the entry-level helmet and the high-

end helmet, an unpaired, two-tailed t-test of unequal variances was employed. A one-way ANOVA was also used to compare the four types of protective head pads and the kendo users comparison. All tests were utilized on GraphPad Prism 9.5.1 analyzer.

III. RESULTS

When the linear accelerations of the entry-level and high-end helmets were compared, there was no significant difference $p = 0.131$ (Table I). The average linear acceleration of the entry-level helmet was 18.92g with a standard deviation (SD, \pm) of 8.072 g forces . The high-end helmet yielded $19.9\text{g} \pm 5.781$ (Table I).

As for the different padding types (C1 = commercial brand 1 padding, C2 = commercial brand 2 padding, H1 = homemade brand 1 padding, H2 = homemade brand 2 padding, NP = no padding), C1 had an average linear acceleration of $22.3 \pm 6.38\text{ g forces}$, C2 with $17.99 \pm 3.958\text{ g forces}$, H1 with $16.42 \pm 2.927\text{ g forces}$, H2 with $16.34 \pm 3.535\text{ g forces}$, and NP with $19.65 \pm 5.939\text{ g forces}$ (Table 2). Through an ANOVA one-way test, the difference of g forces received by the helmet plus padding inserts was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$) (Table 2).

The study results revealed varying linear accelerations among different skill level kendo users. The non-practitioner, 6-kyu, 7-kyu, and Sho-dan exhibited g forces of $28.76\text{g} \pm 7.916$, $18.42\text{g} \pm 5.251$, $14.24\text{g} \pm 4.301$ (7-kyu), and $14.32\text{g} \pm 3.46$ (Sho-dan) respectively ($p < 0.0001$).

(A)

(C)

(B)

Fig. 4. Various Kendo Helmets and Paddings are effective at reducing concussions. (A) Linear acceleration received by the 4-mm entry-level and 2-mm high-end kendo helmets ($p=0.131$). (B) Linear acceleration of a mannequin with five different padding types ($p<1 \times 10^{-4}$). C1 = Commercial Pad 1, C2 = Commercial Pad 2, H1 = Homemade Pad 1, H2 = Homemade Pad 2, NP = no pad. (C) Linear acceleration from different kendo skill levels (ANOVA = $p<1 \times 10^{-4}$). Non-P = non-practitioner, 6-kyu and 7 kyu = beginner level, Sho-dan = master level. Horizontal lines indicate the average. Risk of Concussion = 62.4 g forces.

TABLE I: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF G FORCE READINGS FOR DIFFERENT HELMETS.

	Entry-level	High-end
n	228	235
Avg.	18.92	19.9
SD	8.072	5.781
$p=0.131$		

An unpaired, two-tailed t-test of unequal variances comparing g forces between entry-level and high-end helmets. n = sample size, average (Avg.), and standard deviations (SD) are in g force units (m/s^2).

TABLE II: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF G FORCE READINGS FOR DIFFERENT PADDINGS IN A HELMET

	C1	C2	H1	H2	NP
n	60	62	61	62	62
Avg.	22.3	17.99	16.42	16.34	19.65
SD	6.38	3.958	2.927	3.535	5.939
$p<1 \times 10^{-4}$					

An ANOVA one-way test was used to compare g forces between C1, C2, H1, H2, and NP. n = sample size, Avg. and SD are in g force units (m/s^2).

TABLE III: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF G FORCE READINGS FOR DIFFERENT SKILL LEVELS OF KENDO

	Non-P	6-kyu	7-kyu	Sho-dan
n	57	56	62	53
Avg.	28.76	18.42	14.24	14.32
SD	7.916	5.251	4.301	3.46
$p < 1 \times 10^{-4}$				

An ordinary ANOVA was utilized to compare g forces between varying kendo users n = sample size, Avg. and SD are in g force units (m/s²).

IV. DISCUSSION

The threshold of linear acceleration for concussion varies depending on age and sex, with a risk-for-concussion range between 62.4-146 g forces¹⁹⁻²⁵. In our study, we have chosen to denote 62.4 g forces as the cutoff, as it is the lowest reported value at which there is a risk for a concussion²⁰.

Regardless of the type of armor worn, all linear accelerations measured on the kendo mannequins remained below 62.4 g forces. Interestingly, there was no statistical significance in the linear accelerations received between the entry-level and high-end helmets ($p = 0.131$, Figure 4A). This means that the entry-level helmets offer comparable concussion protection against high-end helmets.

Although all four padding inserts were effective in preventing the risk of concussion since the linear acceleration received by each pad was below the threshold, there was a statistically significant difference ($p < 1 \times 10^{-4}$) in their magnitude of preventing linear head acceleration (Figure 4B). H1 and H2 (Homemade) provided better protection than C1 and C2 (Commercial). Contrary to our expectations of better protection, C1 received on average 2.65 g forces higher than NP and seemed to offer less protection (Table II). On the other hand, C2, H1, and H2 may offer additional protection as they received on average 1.66, 3.23, and 3.31 g forces,

respectively, lower than NP (Table II). Commercial padding inserts may not offer more protection at all.

Congruent with a prior study¹⁰, the kendo non-practitioner had a tendency to hit harder (avg. g force) than those with experience ($p < 1 \times 10^{-4}$). The variation (SD = 7.916 g forces) was much wider for non-practitioners when compared to experienced practitioners who were more consistent in each strike and thus, had narrower variation (Table III). This suggests that additional training in kendo may yield better control and consistency in strike forces. This highlights why beginners are not allowed to wear bogu and participate in full contact practices; the risk of causing concussion to the opponents is high due to lack of control¹².

V. LIMITATION OF WORK

Our study may be limited by the number of hits applied to the two different kendo helmets. With a larger dataset including more kendo practitioners (on both ends of the spectrum for skill level), there may have been a stronger statistically significant difference in the linear acceleration received.

Additionally, the data was collected in a controlled environment instead of during kendo practice or tournaments, which could have additional variables to account for, such as the heat-of-the-moment nature of the sport where strikes may be stronger and faster.

Currently, our study focuses on American practitioners who may employ different styles of kendo in contrast to Japanese kendo swordsmen. To gain a comprehensive understanding, we would like to acquire data from Japanese practitioners and compare it with their American counterparts.

Furthermore, using only one sensor for our readings might have resulted in a lower

accuracy compared to using multiple sensors. In addition, some commercially available helmets feature wider stitch patterns (6 to 8-mm), which differ from the 4-mm stitch pattern we tested. It may be worth further exploring the impact of these variations in future studies.

Lastly, our study did not assess the helmet's durability over time. In light of this, our future research would involve multiple samples and extended data collection over longer periods of time to gain insight into the longevity of protection offered by different kendo protective gear.

VI. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

It may be interesting to further investigate the protective function of helmets with a 2-mm stitch pattern and padding inserts in contrast to helmets with a 4-mm stitch pattern equipped with the same padding. With the limited number of studies in literature, this is an important subject for future research. Evaluating helmets with stitch patterns wider than 4-mm for concussion safety may offer insight into the impact of size variations in stitch patterns (2-mm, 4-mm, 6-mm, & 8-mm). Future research endeavors could prioritize reducing the risk of brain injury resulting from chronic subconcussive blows in kendo by exploring a wider range of materials used in kendo paddings (cowhide, synthetic leather, and deer hide).

VII. CONCLUSION

The results of our study suggest that both entry-level and high-end helmets used in kendo today demonstrate effectiveness in preventing single-blow concussive brain injuries (CBIs). Historically, high-end helmets, which generally have smaller stitch patterns, have been marketed to provide superior head trauma

protection. However, our findings reveal no statistically significant difference in terms of protection between these two types of helmets. Therefore, from a financial and protection standpoint, buying a more expensive helmet may not offer discernible advantages over an entry-level helmet. These findings shed light on the current state of concussion protection in kendo and emphasize the need for further research and equipment regulation to enhance safety measures and reduce the risk of head injuries in this martial art.

Furthermore, our study highlights that certain commercial paddings do not provide additional protection and may cost more than homemade pads that have higher efficacy in preventing concussions. Though the helmets and paddings we tested did not cross the risk-for-concussion threshold, there are other equipment that have yet to be examined for their ability to prevent concussions. Establishing protection standards is especially important as more athletes are returning after the COVID-19 pandemic that had previously put a hiatus on many contact-to-contact interactions, including sports²⁶. This illustrates the need for third-party verification and certification to evaluate the effectiveness of kendo protective gear and help protect consumers from ineffective products.

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